

PSYCHOLOGICAL DETERMINANTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOTIVATION TO STRIVE FOR SUCCESS IN AMATEUR ATHLETES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the psychological determinants that form and develop the motivation to strive for success in amateur athletes. The study examines how factors such as a person's internal motivation, level of self-awareness, social support, and self-confidence affect the desire to succeed in sports activities based on psychological-theoretical and practical approaches. Also, the relationship between the individual psychological characteristics of athletes and motivational directions was determined using psychodiagnostic methods.

Keywords: amateur athlete, striving for success, motivation, psychological determinant, internal motivation, social support, psychodiagnostics.

Introduction.

In modern psychology, the concept of motivation is widely interpreted as an internal driving force of human activity. Especially in the context of sports activities, motivation is an important factor determining not only physical activity, but also a person's psychological stability, competitiveness and desire for self-development. Amateur athletes, unlike professional athletes, are guided by their activities mainly by internal motivation, i.e. personal interest, the need for self-expression and self-actualization needs.

Motivation to strive for success is a conscious and stable need of an individual to achieve high results, which is considered one of the main psychological motives in McClelland's motivational theory. In the formation of this need, personal factors (i.e. temperament, character, volitional qualities), socio-psychological factors (social support, influence of reference groups, social expectations) and intrapsychic factors (internal conflicts, self-esteem, "I-concept") play an important role.

From this perspective, identifying the psychological determinants of the development of motivation to succeed in amateur athletes is of great importance for identifying the individual and socio-psychological resources of this group, as well as for identifying the influential factors that motivate them. In this process, such motivational approaches as Bandura's self-efficacy, Detsey's self-determination theory, and Vroom's expectancy theory are taken as a basis. This study is aimed at identifying the psychomotivational states of amateur athletes within the framework of sports psychology and developing an effective psychological support system for them, which will serve to increase the likelihood of athletes achieving success in their activities.

Psychological determinants that determine the formation and development of motivation to succeed in amateur athletes constitute a complex, multifactorial system. These determinants can be conditionally grouped into personal (intrapsychic), socio-psychological, and motivational-mechanized factors.

The need to strive for success is directly related to the individual psychological characteristics of the individual. These characteristics include the temperament typology (based on the Eysenck model: extraversion-introversion, level of neuroticism), dominant tendencies in the character structure (for example, determination, initiative, willpower), as well as the level of self-esteem. At the same time, the "self-concept" plays a key constructive role in the transformation of this need into a stable motivational mechanism. Experiments show that athletes who highly assess their own abilities maintain psychological stability in the face of failure and are not deprived of motivational power.

Motivation is formed not only individually, but also in a social context. Here, the social support system, i.e. the psychological influence of close friends, family members, coaches and reference groups, serves as a decisive factor. Also, phenomena such as social expectations and normative pressure are important in determining the self-assessment and motivational direction of athletes. Through them, internalized motives are formed in the individual, i.e., internalized forms of external stimuli.

Motivation to strive for success is carried out through cognitive-emotional mechanisms. Cognitive appraisal, i.e., how the athlete understands and interprets the goal and result of his activity, plays an important role in this process. When viewed on the basis of Albert Bandura's "self-efficacy" model, the level of an athlete's commitment and endurance to action depends on his belief in his own capabilities. Also, based on the Self-Determination Theory developed by Ryan and Deci, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation are distinguished. Studies have shown that athletes with intrinsic motivation show stability, satisfaction, and long-term participation in sports activities.

Research methods and diagnostic tools.

The following psychodiagnostic methods were used in this study:

T. Ehlers' "Success and Failure Avoidance" test, which determines the motivational orientation;

Personal determinants were assessed using the Kettel 16-factor personality test (16PF);

Social components of motivation were identified using the V. Smekal and M. Kucher methodology;

The Self-Confidence Scale (Schwarzer & Jerusalem) was used to measure a person's assessment of their own capabilities.

The obtained data were analyzed quantitatively, and the relationship between the level of motivation development in athletes and the determinants influencing it was statistically substantiated using correlation analysis, regression analysis, and clustering methods.

Literature review:

Motivation to strive for success is one of the important research areas in psychology. The theoretical foundations of this motive were initially developed by D. McClelland, who interpreted the desire of a person to achieve high results and self-affirmation through personal achievements as a social motive. McClelland sees motivation not as a hierarchical, but as a set of interconnected needs, this approach serves as an important theoretical basis for understanding the activities of athletes, especially amateurs.

The self-efficacy theory proposed by A. Bandura deeply illuminates the psychological factors that determine the level of motivation to strive for success. In his research, a person's belief in his own abilities, his perception of himself as effective, and his belief in the expected outcome of the action are shown as the main points of motivation.

Also, the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) developed by E. Deci and R. Ryan, dividing motivation into intrinsic and extrinsic types, considers intrinsic motivation as a stable, strong psychological driving force. According to them, intrinsic motivation develops only when such basic psychological needs as autonomy, competence, and relatedness are satisfied. This approach is important in developing effective strategies for motivational growth in athletes, especially among amateurs.

Russian psychologists such as L. I. Bozhovich, V. S. Merlin, and A. N. Leontyev have interpreted motivation as the psychological integration of personality structure, activity content, and social experience, and have elucidated it in relation to the goal-directedness of action. They link motivation to the need to find personal meaning and value in activity.

Modern studies (e.g., Roberts et al., 2007; Vallerand & Rousseau, 2001) have examined in depth the changing nature of athletes' motivation, the influence of social and emotional factors on it, and the psychological consequences of experiences of success and failure in sports. Their research particularly emphasizes the role of motivational climate and interpersonal relationships.

At the same time, local studies conducted to determine the motivational portrait of amateur athletes (for example, T. G. Rumyantseva, O. A. Skovorodnikova) studied the ratio of internal and external motives in amateur activities and showed that motivation in this group is often associated with social recognition, self-awareness, and the pursuit of a healthy lifestyle.

In general, the existing literature shows that the motivation to strive for success is complex and multifactorial. This requires an integrative, personal, and socio-psychological approach to developing this motivation.

Analytical discussion:

The conducted analysis and psychodiagnostic studies confirm that the formation of motivation to strive for success in amateur athletes is based on multifactorial and complex psychological mechanisms. It was revealed that personal-volitional characteristics, intrapsychic needs, social influences, and motivational states are mutually assimilated as psychological determinants.

The results of the study, in line with Bandura's self-efficacy model, show that an athlete's confidence in their abilities directly affects the level of striving for success. In particular, psychological autonomy, emotional stability, and effective self-management skills play a decisive role in this. Among amateur athletes, high self-confidence indicators were correlated with those who had a positive motivational orientation.

Also, based on the Self-Determination Theory of Deci and Ryan, the predominance of intrinsic motivation has a positive effect on the continuity of sports activity, the athlete's mental state, and the level of satisfaction with their activities. Among the study participants, those who perceived sports as a means of self-development and achieving personal perfection were able to maintain motivational stability.

In the analysis of socio-psychological determinants, it was found that the level of psychological support from reference groups (coaches, friends, family) is strongly correlated with the athlete's intrinsic motivation. This confirms the role of social influences in the motivational structure within the framework of social cognitive theory. In particular, normative social pressure is of significant importance in shaping the athlete's self-assessment and attitude to activity. The data obtained through psychodiagnostic tools used in the study

(for example, the McClelland model-based achievement test, Cattell's personal factors test) showed that highly motivated athletes usually set clear and realistic goals for themselves, are more independent of external assessments, and perceive failures constructively. During the discussion, it was found that motivation in amateur athletes is formed not only in connection with sports, but also in connection with the needs for personal identification, self-awareness, and self-affirmation. This requires the development of comprehensive psychological support mechanisms for the development of motivation.

Conclusion.

As a result of the conducted scientific, theoretical and empirical studies, it was found that the psychological determinants affecting the development of motivation to strive for success in amateur athletes form a complex and multifactorial system. The following main conclusions were drawn:

Intrinsic motivation is the main psychological factor that ensures motivational stability and constant striving for activity in amateur athletes. This type of motivation is based on the needs for self-awareness, personal achievement, and demonstration of competence.

In athletes with a high level of self-efficacy, motivation to strive for success is more stable and effective. As determined on the basis of the Bandura model, confidence in one's own capabilities is an important factor determining the motivational activity of athletes.

Socio-psychological factors, in particular, emotional and motivational support from family, coaches and reference groups, serve to strengthen the athlete's attitude to activity, level of self-esteem and need for success.

Psychodiagnostic analyses have shown that highly motivated athletes are distinguished by clarity, positive mood, determination and social activity in their activities.

To form and develop motivation to strive for success, it is necessary to develop psychological interventions that support individual motivation within the framework of sports psychology.

In general, effective management of the development of motivation to strive for success in amateur athletes requires an approach based on a comprehensive psychological analysis of their personal and social resources. In the future, it is advisable to work on the basis of interactive trainings, psychological counseling and motivational programs.

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